

Investigating the Effectiveness of the Financial Narrative Therapy on the Financial Anxiety and Financial Wellbeing among the Female Nurses in the Educational Hospitals

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Abstract

Background and Aim: Researchers in the field of financial health have recently paid attention to the financial wellbeing of individuals and the factors affecting which. Accordingly, various interventions and therapies have been developed so far to maintain and improve the financial health of individuals. The aim of this study was to investigate the effectiveness of financial narrative therapy on reducing the financial anxiety and increasing the financial self-efficacy of female nurses.

Methods: This semi-experimental research is pre-test and post-test with the control group. The statistical population of the study consisted of all female nurses of educational hospitals in year 2019. A total of 30 people were randomly selected and assigned in both experimental and control groups (each with 15 members). In this research, Financial Anxiety Scale (FAS) and Financial Well-Fare Questionnaire (FWQ) were used to collect data. The financial narrative therapy was conducted in eight 90-minute sessions in the experimental group. Data were analyzed using SPSS-v.21 software and Statistical analysis of covariance analysis (ANCOVA).

Results: The findings showed a significant difference between the mean of the experimental and control group in two variables of financial anxiety and financial wellbeing ($P < 0.01$). Based on this, it can be concluded that financial narrative therapy has been effective in reducing the financial anxiety and increasing the financial self-efficacy of the female nurses.

Conclusion: Given the prominence of role of financial issues as a part of life in the today's constantly changing world, and the emergence of multiple sources of stress, financial narrative therapy can be used as an intervention to improve the financial health of individuals.

Keywords: financial narrative therapy, financial anxiety, financial wellbeing, female nurses.

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Introduction

Paying attention to the physical and psychological health of individuals has been always the concern of organizations, institutions and governments both nationally and internationally. The World Health Organization (WHO, 2001, 2004) defines the health as

a form of physical, mental, social well-being, and not merely the absence of disease¹. In the field of psychology, the subjective wellbeing has been the focus of attention of scholars and theorists, with three interconnected but distinct components of emotional, psychological, and social wellbeing; because, according to researchers and theorists' opinion in this area, subjective wellbeing is more effective than any other factor on the mental health of individuals². Financial Health is one of the types of wellbeing that plays an important role in the psychological wellbeing of individuals' life³. Following the changes in lifestyle, the world of jobs, industrialization and restructuring of societies, financial wellbeing has been attracted by researchers in recent years⁴. This term was first introduced by Kim⁵. According to him, the financial well-being is to have the financial security and freedom in the financial choices for the present and future⁶. In other words, financial wellbeing is a condition in which a person can fully fulfill his financial tasks in the present and future, feel secure about his financial future, and is freely able to have the financial choices that lead to pleasure. Financial wellbeing is a structure used to explain the financial position of a person or family. In fact, financial wellbeing is a kind of perceived satisfaction or joy about the financial position⁷. Financial wellbeing can be negatively affected by various variables. Variables such as age⁸, education level, marriage base and income⁹, financial literacy level of individual, poor financial management and financial stress¹⁰ are examples of some variables affecting the financial wellbeing. Increase of the life standards, unhealthy lifestyle habits, various commitments and fluctuations in stress levels are among other factors affecting the financial wellbeing¹¹. Financial Anxiety is one of the factors that can affect the financial wellbeing. Financial Anxiety is a sign and a psychological characteristic that causes an individual to have an unhealthy attitude towards managing his or her finances, and loses the right financial decisions through which, that leads to weakening the financial results and financial anxiety⁶. Financial anxiety can be the consequent of the financial disorder. Persistent financial disorders are predictable, and are often serious and of the kind of destructive financial behavior pattern that cause severe stress, anxiety, and abnormalities in the underlying areas of life¹². According to researchers findings in the field of financial health¹³, nine classes are listed for financial

disorders which include: Compulsive buying disorder, Ambling disorder, Workaholics, Hoarding disorder, Financial dependence disorder, Financial enabling disorder, Financial Infidelity, Financial enmeshment disorder, and Financial denial¹². Financial anxiety can affect both working and unemployed men and women. The negative consequences of the financial anxiety on women are more than men⁶. Mental and physical health is very important in women because they are the basic pillar of the family; however, it can be seen that excessive activity in the workplace, the stress of house chores and child care, and addition to that, and the financial worries threaten their mental health¹⁴. Financial anxiety has negative consequences for individuals¹⁵. Financial anxiety has negative effects of the general wellbeing and financial wellbeing of individuals and is one of the strongest predictors of low levels of wellbeing^{16, 17, 18}. Financial anxiety also has negative consequences on physical and mental health of the individual^{19, 20, 21} and leads to the instability of marital life²².

One of the postmodern therapies is the financial narrative therapy²³ that helps people to overcome the financial anxiety²⁴. Financial narrative therapy is retrieved from the narrative therapy²⁵. Financial narrative therapy provides a therapeutic and theoretical approach to therapist which is a combination of mental health and financial planning models. The combined financial narrative therapy model is designed to be used by the trained professionals in the field of treatment, counseling, coaching, or financial planning²⁶. The narrative therapy has been used by researchers so far in various variables such as financial anxiety management^{23, 27, 28}, financial well-being²⁹ and treatment of financial disorders³⁰. In total, it can be said that economic issues have affected various aspects of mental health and quality of life and have caused anxiety and financial worries. Therefore, it can be stated that financial anxiety treatment is essential for improving the wellbeing and mental health of individuals and is a valuable step in the field of counseling and psychotherapy, family therapy, economic planning and sociology. Studies show that health workers are more susceptible to financial anxiety because of special difficulties in this area⁶. Nursing is also one of the health care jobs. Due to the sensitivity of occupational responsibilities and their continuous interaction with patients, nurses are always exposed to the physical and mental health risks and negative

stresses. Learning how to deal with tensions and mental health problems caused by life issues, especially the economic issues that are highlighted for most people in today’s world can partly improve their ability to cope effectively with life stresses. Considering the fact that there has not been a study on the financial anxiety in the country and in the group of nurses, this study aimed to investigate the effectiveness of financial narrative therapy on the financial anxiety and financial wellbeing of the female nurses working in the educational hospitals in Isfahan city.

Two hypotheses were considered in this study: 1- Financial narrative therapy is effective in reducing the financial anxiety of female nurses. 2. Financial narrative therapy is an effective way to increase the financial self-efficacy of nurses.

Methods and Materials

This semi-experimental research is pre-test and post-test with the control group. The population of this study included all women nurses in public hospitals in Isfahan in 2019. From this society, two educational hospitals (Imam Hossein (AS) and Shahid Beheshti) in Isfahan were randomly selected. After the coordination, the time and place of meeting were informed and a list

of volunteer nurses participated in educational sessions was prepared in the following (45 subjects). During the introductory session, the goals and content of the training sessions were informed, following a list of individuals (43 subjects) who were volunteered. Before selecting the sample, four volunteers refused to continue the co-operation. For screening, financial anxiety scale and financial wellbeing questionnaire were conducted among volunteers, and 30 people whose mean scores were higher in the financial anxiety scale and below the cutoff point in the financial wellbeing questionnaire were selected and randomly assigned in two control and experimental groups. Before the intervention, the purpose of the intervention was described for the two groups in an introduction session and their expectations were explained. Before the intervention, the financial anxiety scale and financial wellbeing questionnaire were firstly performed as a pretest among the members of the experimental and control groups. In the next step, the financial narrative therapy was performed in the experimental group during the eight sessions (90 minutes each session) and at the end, the post-test was again performed among the members of the experimental and control group. A summary of the description of the financial narratives therapy is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Summary of the description of the financial narratives therapy teaching sessions

Sessions	General goals
1st session	Title: creating the good relationship, familiarity with goals, rules and structure of meetings Agenda: Familiarity among the group members, expressing group rules and norms, reviewing the structure and objectives of the meetings, helping members to participate in the group, and establishing a good relationship.
2nd session	Title: Collecting information about members’ financial behavior Agenda: Collecting information (merely financially) and investigating their financial disorders
3rd session	Title: Assessing the financial situation and documenting the financial problems Agenda: Developing financial problems of group members and presenting an illustration of their current financial problems, providing a new definition of the problem.
4th session	Title: Externalizing the financial problem Agenda: Externalizing and reinvigorating the self- financial problem, expressing the effects of the problem on their lives in a variety of ways.

Cont... Table 1. Summary of the description of the financial narratives therapy teaching sessions

5th session	<p style="text-align: center;">Title: Searching for the unique events</p> <p>Agenda: Expressing the past successful personal memories and experiences, and understanding the exceptions and unique events in their own lives despite the externalized problem.</p>
6th session	<p style="text-align: center;">Title: Providing the financial plan and implementation of new financial preferential reports</p> <p>Agenda: Helping members finding new financial narrations, consolidating them and reaching the insight into how they can actually implement their new financial reports.</p>
7th session	<p style="text-align: center;">Title: implementation and performing the financial program</p> <p>Agenda: implementation and performing the financial program, highlighting the strength points, fixing the preferential report</p>
8 th session	<p style="text-align: center;">Title: Financial plan supervision</p> <p>Agenda: Encouraging and strengthening the members' capacity, evaluating the effectiveness of this financial plan and investigating the financial anxiety, submitting a few reports after observing the financial changes in life, summarizing and implementing the post-tests.</p>

In this study, data collection tools were the demographic questionnaire, financial anxiety scale and financial wellbeing questionnaire. The Financial Anxiety Scale has been developed by Archuleta to measure the financial anxiety¹¹. This scale consists of 7 items and its grading method is based on the seven-degree Likert scale (from never equivalent to 1, to seven equivalents always). The total score in this questionnaire is at least 7 and maximum 49, and high scores represent high financial anxiety in a person. The obtained reliability coefficient was obtained by Cronbach's alpha $\alpha = 0.94$ ¹¹. In Iran, this scale has been translated by Akafian and its validity and reliability have been measured³¹. The reliability of the questionnaire was calculated using Cronbach's alpha (92%). Also, the simultaneous validity of this scale with the behavioral log²⁶ was $r = 0.86$, and its divergent validity was obtained with the financial health scale ($r = -0.66$). In this study, the financial wellbeing questionnaire Prawitz et al. was used to measure the financial wellbeing³². This questionnaire contains 8 questions that are made as the self-report. The internal consistency of the questionnaire was reported 96%³². For each question, responses are graded according to

the eight-degree Likert scale (from never equal to 1, to always equal to 8), and high scores represent a high level of financial well-being. In Iran, the financial well-being questionnaire is translated by Akafian and the validity and reliability of which has been investigated³¹. The reliability of the questionnaire was calculated using Cronbach's alpha ($\alpha = 0.91$). Also, the simultaneous validity of this questionnaire with the financial self-efficacy questionnaire ($r = 0.87$) and its divergent validity with the financial anxiety questionnaire ($r = -0.44$) was obtained³³. The inclusion criteria of participants in this study was to obtain a score higher than the cut-off point in the financial anxiety scale, a score lower than the cut-off point in the financial wellbeing questionnaire, and not be treated or educated by another group during the duration of the research. Exclusion criteria in this study were: presence of acute psychological disorders, including psychotic disorders, absence for more than one session, delay of more than twenty minutes in three sessions, failure to perform specified assignments for more than one session.

Statistical Analysis

Data were collected by statistical software SPSS-V.21 and then analyzed by the descriptive statistics indices (mean and standard deviation) and analytical statistics indices (follow-up tests and covariance analysis). Satisfaction to participate in studying, distributing and collecting questionnaires by the researchers at all phases, avoiding mentioning the names on the questionnaires, and obtaining the introduction letter to conduct the study were considered in this study as the ethical considerations.

Results

For analyzing the research hypotheses, the covariance analysis was used with consideration of the assumptions related to the statistical tests. Descriptive indicators related to the pre-test and post-test scores of financial anxiety and financial wellbeing in both

experimental and control groups are shown in Tables 2 and 3. According to the findings, the mean and standard deviation of the age in the experimental group were equal to (633.41 ± 833.8) and in the control group (42.933 ± 10.606) , respectively. In the experimental group, three students had an under-diploma degree (9.4%), six had a diploma degree (18.8%), 13 had an undergraduate degree (4.6%), 7 had a bachelor’s degree (21.9%) and one had a doctoral degree (1 / 3). In the control group, 2 had an under-diploma degree (4.2), five had a diploma degree (10.4), 6 had an upper secondary degree (12.5) and two had bachelor’s degree (4.2). According to the employment status, in the experimental group, 11 people were under contract (34.4%), three contractors (9.4%), five corporate (15.6%) and 11 formal (34.4%) and in the control group, five were under contract (10.4%), two contractors (2/4), two corporate (2/4), and six formals (12.5) (Table 2).

Table 2- Distribution of demographic characteristics of nurses in two experimental and control groups

<i>Statistical index</i>		<i>Experimental group</i>		<i>Control group</i>	
<i>Demographic variables</i>					
<i>Variables</i>		<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Educational degree	Under diploma	3	9.4	2	2.4
	Diploma	6	18.8	5	10.4
	Undergraduate	13	4.6	6	12.5
	Bachelor’s	7	21.9	2	4.2
	Upper Bachelor’s	1	3.1	0	0
	Total	15	100	15	100
Employment status	Based on contract	11	34.4	5	10.4
	Contractual	3	9.4	2	4.2
	Corporate	5	15.6	2	4.2
	Official	11	34.4	6	12.5
	Total	15	100	15	100

Table 3 - Mean and standard deviation of pre-test, post-test scores in the financial anxiety variables

Variables	Group	Number	Pre-test		Post-test	
			Average	Standard deviation	Average	Standard deviation
Financial anxiety	Test	15	30.33	5.47	17.86	4.03
	Control	15	28.26	3.15	27.93	4.11

The results of Table 2 show that in the financial anxiety variable, the mean and standard deviation of the scores of the experimental group in the post test were 17.86 and 4.03, respectively. In the control group were 27.93 and 11.4. Based on the results of this table, it can be concluded that in the financial anxiety variable in the experimental group, the mean post-test scores changed to the pre-test, but no tangible changes are observed in the control group.

Table 4 - Mean and standard deviation of pre-test, post-test scores in the financial wellbeing variables

Variables	Group	Number	Pre-test		Post-test	
			Average	Standard deviation	Average	Standard deviation
Financial wellbeing	Test	15	18.533	2.133	59.866	17.585
	Control	15	15.933	2.463	17.066	10.374

The results of Table 2 shows that in the financial wellbeing variable, the mean and standard deviation of the test group in the post-test were equal to 59.886 and 585.17, respectively, and in the control group were 17.066 and 10.347, respectively. Therefore, it can be concluded that in the financial anxiety variable, the mean of post-test scores changed to pre-test in the experimental group, but no significant changes were observed in the control group. Before using the covariance analysis, a Levin test was used to examine the equations of variances that The results showed that in financial anxiety and

financial wellbeing, the level of significance is greater than 0.05; Therefore, the variances are equal and the use of covariance analysis has no problem and the reliability of its results is confirmed.

The first hypothesis in this study was the financial narrative therapy teaching on reducing the financial anxiety of female nurses. To test this hypothesis, the covariance analysis test was used, results of which are presented in Table 5.

Table 5 - The results of covariance analysis the effect of group membership on the financial anxiety scores

Research variables	Sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	Average of squares	F	Significance level	Squares (impact rate)	Statistical power
Pre-test	293.714	1	293.714	48.389	0.0001	0.632	000.1
Group membership	948.799	1	948.799	149.852	0.0001	0.748	000.1
Error	170.952	27	6.332	-	-	-	-

As shown in Table 5, after the omission of the pre-test effect on the dependent variable and according to the calculated coefficient F, it is observed that there is a significant difference (P = 0.000) among the adjusted averages of the participants' financial anxiety scores in the post-test phase (F = 149.552) in terms of the group membership (experimental group and control group). Therefore, the first hypothesis of the research is confirmed. Therefore, teaching the financial narrative therapy has affected the financial anxiety of the experimental group in the pre-test. The amount of this effect in the post-test phase is 0.847. The second hypothesis of the present study was the effectiveness of teaching the financial narrative therapy on increasing the financial wellbeing of the female nurses. The results of this hypothesis are presented in Table 6.

Table 6 - The results of covariance analysis the effect of group membership on the financial wellbeing

Research variables	Sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	Average of squares	F	Significance level	Squares (impact rate)	Statistical power
Pre-test	754.008	1	754.008	4.005	0.04	0.129	0.488
Group membership	14390.025	1	14390.025	76.442	0.0001	0.739	1.000
Error	5082.658	27	188.247	-	-	-	-

As shown in Table 6, after the elimination of the pre-test effect on the dependent variable and according to the coefficient F, it is observed that there is a significant difference (P = 0.000) among the adjusted averages of the participants' financial wellbeing scores in the post-test phase (F = 149.552) in terms of the group membership (experimental group and control group). Therefore, the second hypothesis of the research is confirmed. Therefore, teaching the financial narrative therapy has affected the financial wellbeing increase of the female nurses in the experimental group. The amount of this effect in the post-test phase is 0.739.

Discussion

The purpose of this study was to investigate the effectiveness of financial narrative therapy on the financial anxiety and financial wellbeing of female nurses. As the results of Table 5 show, there is a significant difference between the adjusted averages of participants' financial anxiety scores in terms of group membership (experimental group and control group) at the post-test level (F = 149.852). Therefore, the first hypothesis of the research about the effectiveness of financial narrative therapy on reduction of the financial anxiety of female nurses was confirmed (P = 0.0001).

The results of this study are consistent with the studies^{24, 27, 23} based on the effectiveness of therapeutic narratives on reduction of the financial anxiety. In explaining this finding of the present study, it can be said that the financial narrative therapy, as a new approach, is to solving the financial problems and the treatment process is so that it help oneself separate the financial problem from themselves, and take control of which, and solve its financial problems, that which plays an important role in controlling anxiety. In this study, adopting a friendly stance combined with a sense of acceptance, without blaming, and based on the mutual respect by therapists, played a significant role in creating a safe and trustworthy environment and people were encouraged to pay attention to their financial lives in the form of stories and narrations and then describe the stories and problems of their past, which was full of defeat and the financial failure. When quoting these stories, people find the problem inside. On this basis, the prevailing feeling will be a feeling of frustration and disappointment. Using the animating technique, as part of the financial narrative therapy process, plays an important role in managing anxiety⁶. In this study, during the financial narrative therapy, people were trained to look at the problem as an alive and external entity, give it a nickname, and deconstruct their narration involving full of trouble. This process led to dominance over the financial anxiety, feeling of coping with oneself, and adoption of appropriate financial solutions for their assets, family members, and society. In fact, the financial narrative therapy is an approach that empowers the individual to look at the financial problem from a new angle and have a new interpretation of their finances²⁹.

The second hypothesis in this study was the financial narrative therapy on improving the financial wellbeing of female nurses. As the results of Table 8 show, there is a significant difference between the adjusted averages of participants' financial anxiety scores in terms of group membership (experimental group and control group) at the post-test level ($F = 76/442$). Therefore, the second hypothesis based on the effectiveness of financial narrative therapy on the financial wellbeing of female nurses at the level ($P = 0.000$) was confirmed. The results of this study were consistent with the study conducted in this field²³ on the effectiveness of the financial narrative therapy on the increase of the financial wellbeing.

According to the findings of this study, the main pillar of the financial wellbeing is to have a sense of dominance over the financial life, and as one of the postmodern therapists, the financial narrative therapy contributes people to making such dominant role by creating a positive look to the past, and using an individual's capabilities to compile and illustrate the future financial life narration. In explaining of finding of the present study, one can say that one of the methods of improving the financial wellbeing of individuals is to recognize the successful experiences that a person has in the past in the financial situations, especially the unpleasant financial situations, and to create a positive look to the past³⁴. With educating attitudes, cognitive skills, and short and medium-term plans, the financial narrative therapy help people gain control over their financial situation. Having a sense of dominance over the financial situation is highly emphasized in the financial narrative therapy, and it is the ultimate goal of most of financial interventions and treatments in the field of financial health³⁵.

In this study, by separating themselves from problems, participants searched their own backgrounds to find the unmatched and unique consequences - or brilliant and pure moments; moments in which they have dealt unlike the narrations fulling of the financial problem, and have had successful experiences. This played a significant role in creating a positive and different look to their financial narrations. According to Klontz et al., having a sense of control over the financial situation plays an important role in creating and improving the individual financial wellbeing. Part of the financial control is mental, which is the result of a person's mental review of his/her performance in the various financial situations⁴. The financial narrative therapy tries to create a sense of financial control in one person by extracting and pulling out the unmatched experiences of an individual in the unpleasant financial situations. In this study, it took a lot of time to discover the brilliant and pure events and occurrence of the customer's financial life by asking the key questions, and in return, people found the ability to discover the unmatched events and occurrences of their lives. In fact, the financial narrative therapy deals with a widespread and extensive view of the financial lives of consumers and the reconstruction of their perspective on their financial past⁹.

The financial narrative therapy approach is not limited to minor modifications in solving one or more specific financial problems in life or in reducing financial anxiety, but it is expected to make a profound change in all aspects of the individual's financial life because it changes the general process of the financial life of a person and is focused on giving meaning to the individual's financial life events. With the help of this treatment, the feelings of autonomy and self-control on the personal life, and on the financial and economic issues were created in clients, which contributed to improvement of the financial wellbeing of participants. Regarding the results of this research, we can say that goal of the financial narrative therapy is paying attention to externalizing the financial problem, creating an external look at the financial problem from different angles and, consequently, creating a preferable narration for the narration of the financial life; Therefore, people with the help of the financial narrative therapy can find a new perspective on the facts, and thus reduce the unhealthy thoughts and attitudes towards their assets; As a result, financial anxiety and distress are reduced. Achieving the financial wellbeing is one of the ultimate goals of the financial interventions and education, whose effects are not only in the realm of personal life, but also in the individual's occupational life and it can also affect the individual productivity in the work environment³⁶.

Conclusion

This study, like other studies, has some limitations. The participants in this study were chosen from the female nurses. Therefore, cautious should be taken in generalizing the results for both genders. The attitude of friable subjects to the tests used their degree of cooperation with researchers, their honesty and their interest in applying educational methods and responding to test questions is a topic that is almost beyond the control of researchers and can affect the results of the research. This research was carried out in a small sample of female nurses of educational hospitals in Isfahan; this also reduces the amount of external validity of the research.

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Ethical Clearance: Researchers have adhered to the basic principles of the Helsinki Declaration in conducting research.

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